

PREPARATION AND THERMAL STUDY OF NANOCOMPOSITES OF HYDROXYAPATITE/ BIODEGRADABLE COPOLYESTERS FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY: Novel nanocomposites composed of hydroxyapatite (HAP) and biodegradable copolyesters synthesized via ring-opening copolymerization of succinic anhydride (SA) and glycidol (GA) were developed. They were characterized by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. The hydroxyapatite/biodegradable copolyesters nanocomposites were prepared through a solvent-cast technique. This paper describes the preparation and microstructure of the HAP nanocrystals and hydroxyapatite/biodegradable copolyesters nanocomposites. The results of these studies are described and discussed.

KEYWORDS: Hydroxyapatite, Biodegradable copolyesters, Nanocomposite, Biomedical applications.

INTRODUCTION

There are an increasing number of people suffering from disease or injury leading to bone loss or bone damage. Traditionally, the autogeneous, allogeneic and synthetic bone grafts being the preferred choice of bone grafting. However, there is a considerable cost associated with these grafts and their availability (e.g. the difference of mechanical properties when compared to human bone and incompatibility) is also limited. Due to these limitations associated with bone grafts, a considerable need for alternative synthetic materials is therefore very critical. Many efforts have been made towards the development of new bone substitute materials such as ceramic or polymer matrix composites for biomedical applications [Devin, Thomson]. Hydroxyapatite (HAP) has been proved to possess feature properties of biocompatibility, ideal hardness, a certain degree of bioactivity, and high resistance to moisture. There are a number of approaches to synthesize HAP. Some of the widely used approaches include aqueous colloidal precipitation [Jarcho], sol-gel [Hsieh], solid-state, and mechano-chemical [Toriyama, ChenCW] methods. In recent years, the preparation of nano-sized HAP has received much attention in order to simulate the nature of bone structure [Coathup]. However, most synthetic apatites are formed via high temperature and complicate processes, resulting in a well-crystallized structure and a larger particle size [Chen], which have little or no activity in bioresorption. Hydroxyapatite (HAP) / biodegradable copolyesters nanocomposites, have

attracted much attention since such composites may have preferable properties such as osteoconductivity due to the presence of hydroxyapatite.

In the present study, the morphology of the nano-sized HAP powders and HAP/biodegradable copolyester nanocomposites have been investigated using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The purpose of the current study was to develop a process in which the HAP can be synthesized directly in the presence of the copolyesters.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of HAP nanocrystals

HAP nanocrystals were synthesized via precipitation reaction followed by hydrothermal method described elsewhere [Hao]. The 200 mL of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ aqueous solution (11.4 wt%) was added to a stirred 400 mL $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ aqueous solution (16.8 wt%) followed by the slow addition of ammonium hydroxide solution to the solution until a pH was 11-12. The reaction is allowed to proceed at room temperature. The resultant precipitates were put into an autoclave and hydrothermally treated at 150°C for 5 h. The hydrothermally treated HAP slurry was washed with several instalments of deionized water. The product was finally dried at 80°C for 12 h.

Preparation of biodegradable copolyesters (PGSA)

Biodegradable copolyesters were prepared by ring-opening copolymerization of succinic anhydride (SA) and glycidol (GA) using $\text{Mg}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$ as initiator at 100°C for 48 h [Maeda].

Preparation of HAP/biodegradable copolyester nanocomposites

HAP dispersion was prepared by dispersing 3 g of HAP nanocrystals in 10 mL of DMF. The solution was ultrasonicated until the HAP powder was thoroughly dispersed in the solvent and filtered at room temperature. Preweighted biodegradable copolyester (PGSA) was added into a flat-bottom flask that contained the HAP dispersion. The flask was sealed off and stirred at room temperature until PGSA totally dissolved into the HAP dispersion. The resulting mixture was put into treated under hydrothermal condition as described before. The HAP/biodegradable copolyester nanocomposite was further dried at 80°C for 12 h and subjected to characterization method.

Characterization of HAP nanocrystals and GA/HAP nanocomposites

Phase analysis of the synthesized nanocrystals and nanocomposites were conducted using X-ray diffraction (XRD). XRD was performed by packing the sample powder onto the glass slide and measured using a X-ray diffractometer (Model RINT-2000 Rigaku) with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation at 40 kV and 40 mA, and a scan rate of $2^\circ(2\theta)/\text{min}$. The crystallite size of the synthesized HAP is expressed by Scherrer's formula as follows [Cullity]: $x = 0.9\lambda / \beta \cos\theta$ where x is the crystallite size of the synthesized HAP, λ of 1.5405 Å is the wavelength of $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$, β is the full-width at half-maximum intensity (FWHM), and θ is Bragg's angle. The morphological characteristic features of the HAP nanocrystals and HAP/biodegradable copolyester nanocomposite were studied using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL JSM-6500 FE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

XRD patterns of commercially available HAP and as-synthesized HAP are shown in Fig. 1. The results indicate that all peaks correspond to the HAP reflections (JCPDS card No. 9-432). Based on the crystallite size analysis using the Scherer equation, the as-synthesized HAP nanocrystal has a crystallite size about 20 nm. The small aggregate contains several nano-sized crystals were observed on SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces of HAP nanocrystals (Fig. 2 (b)), whereas the commercial HAP exhibits the micro-structure (Fig. 2 (a)). These studies are in good agreement with the XRD measurements. The SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces of HAP/biodegradable copolyester (30:70) nanocomposites are shown in Fig. 3. The HAP nanocrystals with particle size around 20 nm were observed on the surface of the copolyester. The results indicate that HAP surface was coated with added biodegradable copolyesters.

Fig. 1: XRD patterns of (a) commercially available HAP and (b) as-synthesized HAP nanocrystals.

Fig. 2: SEM of (a) commercial HAP microcrystals and (b) as-synthesized HAP nanocrystals

Fig. 3: SEM of as-synthesized HAP/biodegradable copolyesters composites

It was found that the casting technique was not appropriate for the fabrication of the nanocomposite of the HAP/PGSA. Further study on compatibility, mechanical and thermal properties (DSC) of the blends as well as molding techniques of the blend are under investigation.

Conclusion

The biodegradable, water soluble fractional copolyesters were synthesized by ring-opening polymerization. The biodegradability of the synthesized polymer was studied. The hydroxyapatite nanocrystal was synthesized via precipitation reaction followed by hydrothermal method and its structure was characterized by XRD and SEM analysis. The synthesized hydroxyapatite nanocrystal was blended with biodegradable copolyester by a solvent-casting technique and characterized by SEM analysis.

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